

COMPLEXITIES OF THE ADOPTION OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS

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Abstract

The maritime sector is in a complex transition toward decarbonization driven by regulatory pressure and sustainability goals (*IMO, 2011,2021,2023; EU, 2022*). Alternative fuels such as hydrogen, ammonia, methanol, DME, and biofuels offer potential pathways, yet their adoption remains challenged by economic, infrastructural, operational, and technical constraints.

This study presents findings from the Baltic Fit Innovation Workshop (*Baltic Fit Project, 2024*), held under the EU Horizon “Baltic Fit” project in collaboration with the Estonian Maritime Cluster. With over 50 stakeholders across shipping, ports, shipbuilding, and services, the workshop provided a rich dataset for evaluating decarbonization priorities. Qualitative and quantitative approaches based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process principles (*Saaty, 1980*) were applied to systematically score and rank themes using repetition and criticality supported by stakeholder validation. Five key evaluation dimensions were established: environmental benefits, economic viability, technical feasibility, infrastructure requirements, and operational challenges. These were weighted based on stakeholder emphasis and assessed against the Poseidon Principles (*Poseidon Principles, 2019*) guiding climate-aligned ship financing (*Tapaninen, 2023*).

Results reveal strong emphasis on environmental benefits (35% weight), particularly for hydrogen and ammonia, while economic viability (30%) and technical feasibility (20%) were critical in shaping transitional pathways. Infrastructure requirements (10%) and operational risks (5%) were relatively underweighted despite their role. The analysis highlights gaps between stakeholder needs and current financial frameworks. For instance Poseidon Principles support emission alignment, but they are not fully inclusive to lifecycle costs, safety measures, and infrastructure financing. By integrating practical challenges with decarbonization goals this study underscores the need for more holistic financial instruments that align with real-world maritime operations.

Implications for sustainable maritime operation

This study contributes to sustainable maritime operations by identifying practical barriers and enablers in the adoption of alternative fuels. It reveals the misalignment between current financial mechanisms and industry needs, particularly in infrastructure readiness and operational safety. The findings suggest the Poseidon Principles could be expanded to include lifecycle costs and safety risks promoting an inclusive decarbonization framework. Aligning financial incentives with technical feasibility and infrastructure development can accelerate the adoption of new fuels supporting international targets set by the International Maritime Organization and the European Union’s Fit for 55 package.

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